

DETECTION AND MONITORING OF MANGANESE IN DRINKING WATER AND GROUNDWATER THROUGH PHOTO-OXIDATION SENSORY REACTION WITH ULTRA-SMALL CARBON NANODOTS

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ABSTRACT. The paper focuses on the development of ultra-small carbon nanodots as sensitive sensors for detection and monitoring of manganese in drinking water and groundwater. The environmental contamination with manganese is often a result from industrial activities such as mining and agriculture. The soluble Mn ions are toxic for many organisms and might even cause serious human diseases. The strategy for sensory detection used by us is based on a photo-oxidation reaction, in which the carbon nanodots are dissolved in acidic solution and illuminated with UV irradiation ($\lambda = 365$ nm). At these conditions the nanoparticles acted as photosensitizer and produced singlet oxygen, which can be monitored by 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine as an organic indicator. However, to proceed this reaction, it is necessary to introduce the redox pair Mn(II)/Mn(III) in the reaction mixture, which plays the role of a catalytic mediator for the electron transfer. Thus, the oxidation of 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine appears, which results in blue colour of the solution with absorbance maximum at 645 nm. The rate of this sensory reaction was significantly enhanced in the presence of EDTA, which was used as a ligand to obtain a stable complex of Mn(III)/EDTA. The formed complex itself oxidised the organic indicator and caused the colorimetric reaction. Among the other metal ions tested, only manganese could be detected by the presented sensory approach.

Keywords: manganese detection and monitoring, ultra-small carbon nanodots, sensory reaction

Introduction

Manganese (Mn) is one of the most abundant metals found in the earth's crust (Chiswell and Huang, 2006). The groundwater percolating through rocks and soil can dissolve various minerals containing Mn (Khadse et al., 2015). In nature, Mn exists mainly in its oxidised chemical forms Mn²⁺ and Mn³⁺ (Armstrong 2008). For example, in aquifers where the amount of dissolved oxygen is low, higher levels of dissolved Mn²⁺ can be found (Zhang et al., 2020). Thus, the highest concentrations of manganese are measured in groundwater, which is a rare phenomenon for the surface water (Dieter et al., 1992). In most studies elevated Mn in groundwater is due to bedrock leaching, but in other cases the pollution can be caused by industrial activities, such as mining, dump sites and agriculture (Wuana and Okieimen, 2011). The overexposure to this transition metal might be toxic to many organisms and their different life stages (O'Neal and Zheng, 2015). Several studies have demonstrated the negative association between elevated Mn in drinking water and the caused human diseases (Vollet et al., 2017).

The atomic absorption spectrophotometric analysis is one of the most widely used chemical methods for monitoring of Mn in the contaminated environment (Bulska and Ruszczynska, 2017). However, the colorimetric, fluorimetric and plasma atomic emission analytical techniques are also recommended for measuring Mn in environmental samples. Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) atomic emission analysis is frequently employed for determination of the total Mn amount, but it cannot distinguish the different oxidation states of manganese (Wilschefski and Baxter, 2019). Although each of these methods is known for its extremely high precision, there are certain drawbacks that make them difficult to access for massive use, particularly in the developing countries. The main obstacle is that their price is too high, i.e. they require huge investments, expensive maintenance, as well as highly qualified staff (Park et al., 2018). In addition, the samples

preparation often involves use of numerous aggressive and toxic reagents, complicated chemical protocols, and diverse approaches or procedures, which might destruct the environmental sample (Bamforth et al., 2006).

In the last decade the carbon nanodots (C-dots) have been developed as promising and environmentally friendly nanomaterials for biosensing and metal ion detection (Tuerhong et al., 2017). For example, fluorescent C-dots were already utilised for detection of Hg²⁺, Ag⁺, Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺ and Ca²⁺ (Loukanov et al., 2018). In all methods the C-dots are prepared by economical and green chemical approach, which makes them appropriate for mass usage in simple analyses instead of the classical expensive analytical techniques. The use of C-dots requires also simple synthesis and sample preparation, common analytical tools as absorbance and fluorescence spectrophotometers.

The purpose of the currently reported work is to develop the carbon nanodots as nanosensors for detection and monitoring of Mn in drinking water and groundwater. For that purpose the photo oxidation properties of C-dots were investigated under irradiation with 365 nm UV light. Under these conditions the C-dots acted as photosensitizers and generated singlet oxygen (¹O₂). The process is pH dependent and the presence of singlet oxygen can be monitored by oxidation of an organic indicator as 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB). However, in aqueous solution the migration of ¹O₂ is very short and the deactivation to its triplet state is occurring very fast. So, to proceed with the process of photo oxidation it is necessary to have the cooperation of a mediator that might enhance the efficiency of electron transfer. Manganese was chosen as an appropriate candidate for this role, because Mn³⁺ possesses strong oxidation power. This was the key step in our investigation toward development of nanosensor for manganese. The adding of Mn²⁺ to the aqueous solution significantly enhanced the oxidation of TMB. This process occurred with very high efficiency at slightly acid

pH of the reaction mixture. In case of other metals this effect was not observed. Only Mn^{2+} demonstrated such enhancement of the photo oxidation reaction, and therefore our efforts were concentrated to develop this reaction as a sensory process.

Experimental Procedures

Materials and analytical instrumentation

All chemicals used in the protocols below were of analytical-reagent grade. Sodium acetate (CH_3COONa), citric acid ($C_6H_8O_7$), ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid disodium salt ($C_{10}H_{14}N_2O_8$ Na_2 , EDTA), ethylenediamine (EDA) and all metal chloride salts were purchased from WAKO. 3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich and dissolved in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) to generate a freshly prepared stock solution. UV-VIS spectroscopy was performed on UV-VIS Jasco analytical spectrophotometer (model No V-570) using 1 cm quartz cuvette. The UV-VIS absorption spectra were taken of C-dots (5 $\mu g/mL$), Mn(III)-EDTA (10 mM Mn(II), 20 mM EDTA) and oxidised TMB (0.8 mM, pH 3.5-7.5). The nanoparticle emission was quantitatively measured by photoluminescence spectrophotometer (Jasco analytical photoluminescence UV-VIS, model No FP-6300). The fluorescence lifetime of C-dots with different concentration of manganese were measured on a Fluorolog-3 spectrophotometer with a DeltaDiode (370 nm excitation) as the excitation source and a picosecond photon detection module as the detector. The phosphorescence spectra of the generated singlet oxygen by irradiation of C-dots with UV light were recorded also by a Fluorolog-3 spectrophotometer. The electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) measurements were conducted with 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine (TEMP) as spin traps for measurements of singlet oxygen levels. For that purpose 5 μL aqueous solutions of C-dots (concentration = 10 mg/mL) and 25 μL of TEMP (10 M) were mixed with 2 mL of buffer (at pH = 7.5 and 4.0) to identify 1O_2 . The resulted mixed solution was irradiated by UV with 365 nm wavelength (LED light) for 60 seconds before EPR measurement. The observed visual color was captured by professional digital photo camera Nikon D3800 (Japan).

Synthesis of ultra-small carbon nanodots

The carbon nanodots were synthesised from citric acid and 1,2-ethylenediamine by microwave assisted pyrolysis, which is known as a bottom up method. In short, mix of 1 g citric acid and 0.2 ml 1,2-ethylenediamine in 10 ml ultrapure water was subjected to microwave irradiation for 180 seconds. The carbon nanoparticles in the obtained crude product were purified from the by-products by dialysis and centrifugation in acetone solution. The obtained nanoparticles are kept in aqueous solution at $-20^\circ C$ in a refrigerator for a long period of time. The C-dots quantum yield was measured by absolute photoluminescence quantum yield measurement system (model No C9920-03G, Hamamatsu, Photonics). The electron microscopic images were obtained by FEI tecnai G2 20 transmission electron microscope (TEM) at 120 kV accelerating voltage. The samples were prepared by placing the aqueous droplets of C-dots onto a carbon-coated copper grid. In order to confirm the average nanoparticle diameter dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurement of filtered C-dots was performed (Brookhaven Instrument Corporation, model No BI-200SM).

Colorimetric detection and monitoring of manganese

Two stock solutions were prepared for the colorimetric assay experiment. Solution I contains TMB in EDTA. For that purpose 11.5 mg EDTA (0.001 M, 0.0116 g) was dissolved into 40 ml ddH₂O (MilliQ water). 7.7 mg of TMB were preliminary dissolved in DMSO and added into 40 ml stock solution I. Solution II contains C-dots with concentration 33 mg/ml. For the photo-oxidation reaction assay 20 μL of C-dots (solution II) was added into 1.5 mL TMB in EDTA (solution I) in an Eppendorf. Then, an aliquot of 20 μL aqueous solution of the metal chloride (Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+}) was added to the Eppendorf assay to achieve the final concentration of 0,001 M. The assay was irradiated with UV lamp (365 nm wavelength LED light) for 1 min and the blue colour change was measured by a UV-VIS Jasco analytical spectrophotometer.

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the photochemical reaction of singlet oxygen generation, as well as TMB oxidation through mediation with manganese as a catalyst (A). Absorption spectra of (B) mixture of C-dots and reduced form of TMB and (C) mixture of C-dots, EDTA, manganese ions (1 mM) and oxidised form of TMB after illumination with UV irradiation

Results and discussion

The irradiated with UV light ($\lambda = 365$ nm) C-dots are able to convert the oxygen molecule from triplet state ($^3\text{O}_2$) to singlet electronic state ($^1\text{O}_2$) as shown in the photochemical reaction (Fig. 1A). Because of differences in their electron shells, the singlet oxygen is much more reactive in comparison to the triplet oxygen. It is pH-dependent (usually $\text{pH} < 4.5$) and as a result the TMB is oxidised and the reaction solution colour turns to blue. Without manganese as a catalyst, the UV irradiation alone cannot oxidise TMB. Manganese is a good candidate as a mediator, because the Mn^{3+} ion from the redox pair Mn(II)/Mn(III) has strong oxidation power, stability and significantly enhances the efficiency of the electron transfer. The reaction can be significantly improved in the presence of EDTA. We have assumed that the aqueous Mn(II) can be stabilised by these ligands, i.e. the formation of Mn(III) EDTA complex. Without EDTA the reaction of photo-oxidation occurred only in acidic pH condition. Nevertheless, if EDTA is added TMB can be oxidised even at neutral pH. The reason that this reaction proceeds under the UV illumination is that the C-dots absorption peak is located around 350 – 360 nm (Fig. 1B). After illumination with 365 nm light, an absorption peak at 645 nm emerged (Fig. 1C) and the reaction solution turned to blue colour. The stability of Mn(III)/EDTA complex enabled a detailed study of the photo-oxidation sensory reaction. For example, the illumination step can be separated from the oxidation reaction. This was observed when TMB was added 5 min after turning off the UV-lamp. Because the solution still contained Mn(III)/EDTA complex at that time, the oxidation of TMB occurred instantaneously. Nevertheless, without the presence of EDTA or UV this delayed reaction of post oxidation did not occur. Thus, the role of generated Mn(III) and its stability was confirmed. In our experimental setup the C-dots acted as a nanosensor photosensitizer and the presence

of detected manganese did not quench their fluorescence at 460 nm. The sensory reaction proceeded because Mn(II) can be oxidised to Mn(III) by the dissolved oxygen, but the rate of this reaction normally is too slow. So, the results in our experiment suggested that the generation of oxygen in singlet state was responsible for the oxidation of Mn(II) . In order to confirm this hypothesis we analysed the phosphorescence emission of $^1\text{O}_2$ at 1725 nm (as shown on Fig. 2A). By this analytical method it is possible to observe directly the red glow of the sample due to the singlet oxygen contents. As shown, the emission possesses high intensity phosphorescence peak (above 4000 a.u.). If Mn(II) was added into a solution of C-dots in $\text{CD}_3\text{CN} - \text{D}_2\text{O}$ mixed solvent ($v/v = 15/1$) the intensity decreased by about 40-45 %. However, if EDTA is added too, the phosphorescence of singlet oxygen completely disappeared. Therefore, the role of Mn(II) is not to produce any peroxides but just to oxidise and form Mn(III) , which is a strong oxidant and reacts with TMB as shown on the equation (Fig. 1A). Taken together Mn(II)/Mn(III) act as a catalytic mediator, which is the main reason for the unique sensory reaction. To test this observation we tried an assay of nine other metals (Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+}), which are known as common pollutants of the environment. As shown on Fig. 2B, among them only Mn^{3+} ion is characterised with the ability to oxidise TMB. Some other metals can also form redox pair ($2+/3+$), for example Co(II)/Co(III) or Fe(II)/Fe(III) but they are not powerful enough to oxidise TMB and change the colour of the reaction solution into blue. Although cobalt is also a strong oxidiser, the form of Co(III) is unstable at these conditions or it does not react with TMB. The absorption spectrum of all these metals even in the presence of EDTA did not change significantly the absorbance at 645 nm when irradiated with UV light.

Fig. 2. (A) Phosphorescence spectra of singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) induced by the irradiated C-dots in $\text{CD}_3\text{CN} - \text{D}_2\text{O}$ mixed solvent. (B) Test of metal cations with concentration 1 mM to oxidise TMB in the presence of EDTA (1 mM) and under illumination with UV light $\lambda = 365$ nm. The absorbance intensity was measured at 645 nm. Among tested metals only manganese has an ability for enhanced oxidation. (C) Data from DLS analyses. (D) TEM micrograph of the synthesized C-dots

As mentioned above the ultra-small C-dots act as photosensitizer nanosensor for the detection and monitoring reactions of manganese. Their size distribution was revealed by combining dynamic light scattering (DLS) and transmission electron microscopic (TEM) observation. DLS analysis (Fig. 2C) demonstrated that the nanoparticle hydrodynamic diameter is distributed in the range of 2 – 6 nm with an average value of 3 nm. These data were supported by TEM observation and measurement (Fig. 2D). C-dots appear on the micrograph as nanoparticles, which are uniform in size. Their shape is spherical. From the TEM image, only the bigger nanoparticles (diameter > 3 nm), which have higher contrast from the background granularity of the carbon film, could be distinguished. And even so, sometimes it is challenging to distinguish the right location and the outlines of the low contrasted nanoparticles, because the imaging of predominantly carbon structures on carbon grids does not allow the precise determination of the objects.

Conclusion

We have developed ultra-small carbon nanodots as nanosensors for detection and monitoring of manganese in water. The specificity of sensory reaction is based on the unique properties of Mn(II) ions to catalyse and enhance the oxidation rate of TMB in the presence of singlet oxygen produced via photosensitisation of illuminated C-dots with UV light. The photo-oxidation induced reaction is effective in acidic pH and the presence of EDTA used as ligand for Mn(III)/EDTA complex formation. The reported protocol for sample preparation and analytical data can be used for selective and sensitive detection of manganese in contaminated environmental samples, including environmental impact assessment.

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